

Impact of Operational Performance and Service Quality Experience on Customer Satisfaction and Loyalty

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Abstract

Background: A significant trend in the financial industry is embedded banking (EB), which incorporates banking services straight into platforms or apps developed by third parties. In addition to providing consumers with advantageous circumstances, this also presents chances for market expansion and value addition for the bank. Banks will be able to maximise these services if they can drive customer loyalty (CLT) through customer satisfaction (CST) by boosting the operational performance (OPF) and service quality experience (SQE).

Objective: This article aimed to investigate the impact of OPF and SQE on CLT. Additionally, the study sought to understand the mediating role of CST in the relationship between SQE and CLT, as well as the mediating role of OPF in the relationship between CST and CLT.

Methodology: The study sample comprises 318 customers who use EB services in Vietnam. The data was analysed in two stages and processed using Smartpls 4.0 software.

Result: The results show that SQE, OPF and CST have a positive impact on CLT. CST and OPF were also found to have a mediating role in the relationship between SQE and CLT, and between CST and CLT, respectively.

Conclusion: The results demonstrate that improving SQE, OPF, and CST can significantly boost customer loyalty in EB services, especially when CST and OPF serve as mediators. This provides practical insights for Vietnamese banks to develop more competitive and customer-focused digital strategies.

Unique Contribution: This study not only adds to the Theory of Planned Behaviour but also provides practical data for bank managers to formulate effective policies and solutions.

Key Recommendation: Bank managers need to focus on the factors that make up a positive CLT of EB services. In addition, considering the factors that drive SQE, OPF, and CST should also be focused on through a variety of activities.

Keywords: Commercial Bank, Customer loyalty, Customer satisfaction, Embedded Banking, Service Quality.

Introduction

EB services, integrated directly into non-financial platforms, not only bring convenience to customers but also an opportunity for banks to expand their customer networks and increase revenue (Wullweber, 2020). However, to optimise value from these services, banks need to understand how SQE, OPF, and CST affect customer loyalty (CLT). One of the key features of EB is that the customer experience process and the product and service delivery process time and occur simultaneously. EB services cannot be mass-produced, stockpiled, and sold in the same way as other products. Unlike traditional services, the impact of exposure on the service experience is unclear. Therefore, the factors that increase the customer experience when using traditional banking services may no longer be true in the provision of EB services. Meanwhile, customer experience research on EB services is minimal and almost limited to developed countries.

Previous research confirms the positive impact of OPF, SQE and CST on CLT (Lee & Seong, 2020). This effect shows that customers with positive experiences for various reasons become repeat buyers or become loyal buyers. The results also show that an increase in market share will lead to an improvement in the number of loyal customers. However, these general premises are not suitable for all industries or all conditions. Previous research suggests that increased sales or market shares do not always improve CLT (Nelly Tochi Nwosu et al., 2024). This is frequently the consequence of subpar marketing, low relative value, and numerous other macro issues. Therefore, positive experiences from the buyer's side often lead to improved CLT, but not in all studies. This impact may vary depending on the macroeconomic situation and the operational context of commercial banks in different countries. Therefore, it is necessary to study and evaluate the specific impacts of OPF, SQE and CST on CLT of commercial banks in Vietnam.

In Vietnam, although EB services have developed and have been introduced to customers by some banks. However, in practical terms, customer awareness of this service is still an issue that Vietnamese banks need to pay attention to. The impact of SQE and OPF on CLT still needs to be clarified. More specifically, the discovery of the role of intermediary, or the channel that transmits the impact of SQE on CLT of commercial banks through CST has not yet had clear results. Especially in the context of a country with a developing financial market like Vietnam. This is an important research gap.

The objective of this study is to assess how SQE, OPF and CST affect CLT of customers using EB services. More importantly, the study considers the mediating role of CST and OPF thereby proposing policy implications to help commercial banks in Vietnam improve EB services and boost CLT. The following content of the article is structured into 5 parts, including theoretical basis, research method, research result, discussion and management implications.

Literature Review

Embedded banking services

EB is the incorporation of financial services into the business platform of a non-financial company or business organization (Hensen & Kötting, 2022). With a payment application, EB service helps users access many different services such as insurance, shopping and air tickets. When joining any e-commerce site, shoppers can easily choose payment methods, even buy now and pay later. This service brings great opportunities to the financial market in general and business opportunities in particular. EB services are considered one of the mechanisms to integrate financial services to increase customer experience at a low cost. By bringing financial services directly to the point of need, EB will accurately meet the ever-changing needs of customers. This meets the increasing needs of customers. EB offers a high-quality and personalized consumer experience, including convenient payment and financing options (Caldecott, 2022). This result promotes OPF in the digital age. EB has then made banking products an invisible but ubiquitous part of everyday life.

Theory of Planned Behaviour

This paper relies on the Theory of Planned Behaviour (TPB) to propose a research model. TPB is developed and improved from the Theory of Rational Action (TRA), in which TRA shows that behaviour is determined by intention. The relationship between intention and behaviour has been given and tested experimentally in many studies in many fields. The two main factors that influence intention are personal attitude and subjective norms. In particular, an individual's attitude is measured by beliefs and evaluations of that behavior. Subjective norms are perceptions of influencers who think that the individual should or should not perform the behaviour. TPB comes from the limitation of behavior that humans have little control over (Khalid et al., 2022). The third factor that influences intentions is the perceived behavioural control factor. Behavioral control perception reflects how easy or difficult it is to perform an act and whether the performance of that behavior is controlled or restricted. TPB and TRA can be considered the first theories to explain the impact of cognition on human behaviour, setting the stage for further studies to exploit this aspect. This is also one of the bases for building the research model.

Research hypothesis

SQE is the customer's evaluation, perception, and affection of all direct and indirect meetings with the bank related to the purchase behaviour. It includes communication meetings, service meetings, and consumer meetings. Business leaders believe that SQE is an important factor in competitiveness. Based on the research results by Kim and Choi (2013), the article proposes to measure SQE by three factors, including quality of service results, quality of interaction, and quality of peers.

Research by Windasari et al. (2022) shows that SQE is considered a comprehensive evaluation index to measure customer post-purchase usage, including time spent or the number of uses. Specifically, a higher level of SQE indicates that customers have been using the product for a longer period. In the financial services industry, SQE should be considered as one of the key predictors of loyalty. This is completely consistent with the implications of the TPB theory. However, other research suggests that SQE is not a reliable predictor of buyer loyalty. According to Rohella et al. (2024), a buyer with good experiences is not necessarily a loyal buyer. So, the main emphasis is that loyal customers always have a positive SQE, but customers with a positive

experience are not always loyal. True loyal buyers have both behavioural loyalty, expressed by a high number of product purchases, and a loyalty mentality influenced by the experience through a positive and strong attitude.

In this study, customers may have a strong positive attitude but don't use the service regularly, known as latent loyalty. However, customers have used a product multiple times but still don't have a strong attitude toward that service, known as fake loyalty. Overall, there are three possible relationships. The first is that customer experience affects loyalty. The second is loyalty which affects the customer experience in the next service experience. The third is that there is no real correlation between customer experience and loyalty. There are so many studies that have shown a relationship between customer experience and loyalty, so the third relationship is discarded. Therefore, the following hypothesis is formulated:

Hypothesis H1. SQE has a positive effect on CLT.

TPB theory states that CST is determined by the experience of EB service quality (Ajzen & Driver, 1992). Studies related to this relationship have received more attention, especially in the context of digital banking services. Customer satisfaction is defined as the customer's reaction to experiencing a product or service provided at an expected or unexpected value level. Customer satisfaction is a measure of quality, value, and customer expectations. Based on this concept, it shows that customer satisfaction is closely related to customer experience. Kumar et al. (2022) have shown that SQE has a significant relationship with CST in India. However, as the level of customer experience increases, this feeling will gradually decrease, leading to lower satisfaction performance. Although there are many studies conducted on digital banking, the evaluation results for EB services have not been clearly defined, especially in the context of Vietnam's financial market. Based on the theoretical basis and the contents argued above, the following research hypothesis is proposed:

Hypothesis H2. SQE has a positive impact on CST.

The operation of commercial banks depends a lot on CST and it is the premise for providing repeat transactions. Suppliers who are not constantly pleasing customers face the risk of losing those customers, resulting in shrinking sales and declining market share over time. This is especially true in the financial services industry, where buyers increasingly expect greater efficiency from new technologies. Customers tend to find improvements in security and safety, otherwise, their satisfaction levels will decrease. Increasing competition in the financial services sector makes it easier for customers to shift their preferences to better banks. Previous research has shown that an increase in CST in the banking industry leads to a higher market share (Kumar et al., 2022). In Vietnam, EB services have been developed recently, so there is also a need for discoveries in this emerging market. Based on the results of previous studies, the article proposes the following research hypothesis:

Hypothesis H3: CST has a positive impact on OPF.

Most studies show that CLT are positively related to market share (Jahan & Shahria, 2022). When the market becomes more mature and enters a saturation phase, the cost of increasing market share becomes more expensive, and improving maintain market share to stabilize profit margins is one of the viable means to increase the loyalty base. Previous research found that brands with large

markets often have more loyal buyers. This is because as buyers switch between brands, a percentage of those who convert are still preferring to choose the big brands. As larger banks get more picks, these banks will gain market share over time. Another explanation is that customers can use the popularity of the brand as an indicator of quality, which leads to more usage from new customers. The following research hypothesis is then proposed:

Hypothesis H4: OPF has a positive impact on CLT.

Loyalty is an extremely solid guarantee of a favourite product, brand, or service to be acquired, or continuously purchased in the future. If an organisation wants to improve their performance, customer retention, and loyalty, it should focus on satisfying its customers. Satisfaction will help increase profitability, customer retention, and loyalty. Organizations in the process of competing for customer loyalty should first focus on satisfaction. Satisfaction is another premise of customer loyalty, which is seen as a significant success for the business. Dissatisfied customers tend to seek information about other options and are more susceptible to incentives from competitors, compared to satisfied customers. Research on digital banking services indicates that there is a positive effect of customer satisfaction on customer loyalty. Customer satisfaction has an effect that is both positive and negligible on customer loyalty. On that basis, the research hypothesis proposed by the author is:

Hypothesis H5: CST has a positive impact on CLT.

When customers experience high-quality service, such as convenience, safety, and smart integration, they develop loyalty through long-term trust and commitment. This loyalty not only increases the frequency of using the service, but also creates a stable source of revenue, reduces the cost of reaching new customers, and promotes positive promotion from customers through word of mouth. Moreover, customer loyalty contributes to building brand reputation, increasing competitiveness, and improving the overall performance of the bank. When customers experience high-quality service, such as convenience, security, and seamlessness in transactions, their satisfaction levels increase by feeling that their needs are being met and expectations are exceeded. This satisfaction encourages customers to increase service usage, refer others, and reduce service churn. These positive behaviours have a direct impact on revenue, OPF, and competitiveness. So, investing in an SQE not only improves satisfaction but also optimizes OPF through stronger engagement from customers. Research by Ramanathan et al. (2017) for 605 customers shows that SQE affects customer behaviour, which in turn leads to the performance of retail businesses in the UK. Another study by Mbama & Ezepe (2018) for digital banking services in the UK has also confirmed the mediating role of CST and CLT on the influence of SQE on OPF. However, this study only evaluated the overall experience and emphasized financial performance. Therefore, there needs to be more general research on SQE and OPF, especially for EB services at Vietnamese commercial banks. The following research hypothesis is then proposed:

Hypothesis H6: CST has a positive mediating impact on the effect of SQE on OPF

In the context of increasingly fierce competition in the financial services sector, especially EB services, CST is considered an important factor in promoting CLT. However, this relationship is not only directly linear but also affected by OPF. Specifically, as CST increases, businesses tend to improve OPF through process optimization, service quality, and enhanced customer experience. High OPF helps businesses maintain stability, minimize service errors and provide outstanding

value, thereby increasing customer trust and commitment. Therefore, OPF plays an intermediary role, amplifying the positive impact of CST on CLT, rather than just a direct impact. The study in Korea demonstrated the mediating role of CST in the relationship between OPF and CLT in the field of education. Currently, no research has been conducted for EB services. From there, the article proposes the following research hypothesis:

Hypothesis H7: OPF has a positive mediating impact on the effect of CST on CLT

Research Methodology

Research design

In this study, to analyse CLT using EB services at Vietnamese commercial banks, the authors used TPB theory. Based on previous studies around the world, this study builds a scale on CLT. An in-depth interview method was conducted with EB service users to identify the factors affecting CLT. The results obtained the final questionnaire consisted of 19 observation variables. The proposed research model is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Research model

Scale measurement

The scale used in the study is inherited from the original scale in previous studies and is justified to suit the context (Table 2). The questionnaire has derived from four observation variables, together with supplementary questions about personal information and information screening. Before going into the official survey, the questionnaire with these scales was sent to 5 experts and 10 customers who have been using EB to receive feedback on the coherence, ease of understanding, and clarity of the form and content of the questionnaire. Statements are measured on a 5-point Likert scale from the lowest point 1 as "strongly disagree" to the highest point of 5 as "strongly agree".

Data collection

The data was collected from November to the end of December 2024. Subjects to participate in the survey are people who are 18 years old or older and have purchased and are using EB. The data is collected through two forms, including the Internet and face-to-face interviews. The questionnaire is sent directly to customers using EB services in Vietnam. At the same time, the author also created an online survey form on Google Forms and shared the survey link via the authors' social media accounts. The number of valid answers collected is 318. Table 1 presents the characteristics of the respondents. To analyze the data, the author used SmartPLS 4.0 software.

Table 1. Characteristics of sample respondents

Characteristics	Frequency	Percent
Gender		
Female	165	52
Male	153	48
Age		
Under 30	127	40
31-35	130	41
36-40	45	14
Over 40	16	5
Work experience		
Less than 2 years	29	9
2-5 years	114	36
5-10 years	102	32
Over 10 years	73	23
N = 318		

Empirical findings

Evaluation of the measurement model

To evaluate the measurement model, the article performs an evaluation of convergent validity, consistency reliability, and discriminant validity. Specifically, the outer loading value of all items must be greater than 0.7 (Hair et al., 2021). The convergent validity of the scale is also evaluated through the AVE, this ratio is accepted when the AVE is greater than 0.5. Consistency reliability is assessed through Cronbach's Alpha (0.6 – 0.9). Discriminant validity is evaluated by Heterotrait-Monotrait Ratio (HTMT). The results are presented in Table 2.

Table 2. Constructs and their Responding Measures

Code	Item	Loading	CR	AVE
Service quality experience (SQE)		Source: H. Kim & Choi (2013)		
SQE1	EB services provide customers with good quality.	0.762	0.932	0.622
SQE2	I believe that the bank provides premium EB services to its customers.	0.800		
SQE3	I affirm that the bank provides EB services that meet the requirements of customers.	0.757		

SQE4	The quality of interaction between me and the EB services is excellent.	0.790		
SQE5	The bank and the staff of the bank that provides the EB services I am using are interested in the customer	0.718		
SQE6	The quality of my interactions with other customers at the bank that provides EB services for me is excellent.	0.783		
SQE7	I interact with stakeholders better when using the EB services.	0.825		
SQE8	My experience with the EB services was excellent.	0.793		
SQE9	I had a superior experience using EB services.	0.798		
SQE10	My experience with the bank as a whole is great	0.853		
Customer satisfaction (CST)		Source: Ayinaddis et al. (2023)		
CST1	I am satisfied with the decision to use EB services.	0.880	0.831	0.747
CST2	I find it very interesting to choose the EB services.	0.868		
CST3	I think I did the right thing by using the EB services.	0.844		
Customer loyalty (CLT)		Source: Ayinaddis et al. (2023)		
CLT1	I would encourage friends and relatives to use EB services.	0.897	0.808	0.724
CLT2	I am highly likely to use EB services shortly.	0.887		
CLT3	I will continue to use EB services even if there is another bank's better service.	0.762		
Operational performance (OPF)		Source: Ahamed et al. (2021)		
OPF1	The bank provides impeccable financial services through EB services.	0.853	0.831	0.747
OPF2	The bank meets customers' expectations for EB services.	0.914		
OPF3	I am satisfied with the bank's EB services.	0.824		

The results show that all outer loadings ranged from 0.718 to 0.914, and AVE ranged from 0.622 to 0.747. These results meet the convergent validity. In addition, the results also show that Cronbach's Alpha was in the range of 0.808 to 0.932. This implies that the results meet the consistency reliability threshold. Table 3 shows the results of the discriminant validity measurement, all HTMT ranged from 0.582 to 0.831 (Table 3), meeting the requirement.

Table 3. Results of discriminant validity

	CLT	CST	SQE
CST	0.678		
SQE	0.730	0.831	
OPF	0.582	0.737	0.640

Abbreviation: *SQE*: Service quality experience; *CLT*_Customer loyalty; *CST*_ Customer satisfaction; *OPF*_ Operational performance.

Evaluation of structural model

Table 4. Hypotheses testing of structural model

Hypothesized relationships	Proposed effects	Standardized regression weight	Results
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H1: SQE → CLT	Positive	0.517***	Supported
H2: SQE → CST	Positive	0.749***	Supported
H3: CST → OPF	Positive	0.618***	Supported
H4: OPF → CLT	Positive	0.398***	Supported
H5: CST → CLT	Positive	0.224***	Supported
H6: SQE → CST → CLT	Positive	0.316***	Supported
H7: CST → OPF → CLT	Positive	0.300***	Supported

*Abbreviation: SQE_Service quality experience; CLT_Customer loyalty; CST_ Customer satisfaction; OPF_ Operational performance; *** $p < 0.001$.*

The results of the Bootstrap test with the number of repeated observations of 500 times are presented in Table 4. The regression coefficients of Service quality experience (SQE), Operational performance (OPF), and Customer satisfaction (CST) are all statistically significant at 1%. Thus, all of the above factors have a positive effect on CLT at Vietnamese commercial banks. Accordingly, the effect on CLT is arranged from strong to weak as follows: service quality experience (SQE), Operational performance (OPF) and customer satisfaction (CST). The effect coefficients were 0.517, 0.398, and 0.224, respectively. The results also show that SQE has a positive effect CST with standardized regression weights of 0.749. CST have have a positive correlation with OPF (0.618). The mediating effect of CST and OPF has also been confirmed with effect levels are 0.316 and 0.300, respectively.

Discussion

The results show that SQE, CST, and OPF have a positive impact on CLT. This result confirmed the H3, H4, and H5 hypotheses and is consistent with the findings of previous studies by Shafique and Ahmad (2022). When the experiences of services are of high quality, value, and reliability perceptions improve in customers, building trust and repeated interactions. This, in turn, enhances customer loyalty, where satisfied customers are more likely to stay with the business and recommend its services to others. Customer satisfaction, resulting from meeting or exceeding customer expectations, reinforces the emotional bond with the brand by encouraging positive word-of-mouth and reducing churn rates. These factors all contribute together to bring better performance from operations by increasing revenues through predictable retention, optimizing resource use, and engendering a positive brand reputation that brings new customers in while retaining old ones.

SQE is found to have a positive impact on CST. This result supports the H2 hypotheses. The results are similar to the study by Makudza (2021). In particular, the relationship between SQE and CST is strongest. With EB services integrated into other platforms, such as e-commerce applications or digital wallets, customers can access immediate and easy financial transactions, thus strengthening their overall experience. It helps when customers consider that these services work seamlessly, are reliable, and can cater to their individual needs in no time. Further, satisfaction creates a better perception while laying the ground for loyalty and continued use. High-quality interactions with EB services also include influencing their users to recommend those services to more people, to contribute better towards sustaining the bank in the highly competitive market.

The mediating role of CST and OPF is also confirmed. This result confirms the H6 and H7 hypothesis, which is consistent with the study by Mbama and Ezepue (2018). If the customers are served better, they are satisfied with the ease, speed, and reliability of the service and will also be loyal to the bank. Overall, the satisfaction of the customers leads them to consume more, be less inclined to defect to competitors, and have increased brand equity. Simultaneously, customer loyalty brings about consistent revenue and also facilitates organic advertising in the form of positive word-of-mouth. These latter factors again contribute directly to improving the bank's performance through customer capture and retention, optimization of operational costs, and entrenchment of a competitive position in the market. In particular, the mediating role of customer loyalty and satisfaction in Vietnam is increasingly recognizable with the advancement in Fintech and demand for integrated financial services, meaning such sustainable success in banks will continuously be appreciable.

Management implications

The results show that SQE has a positive impact on CLT and CST. Therefore, bank administrators need to focus on the quality of EB services. Banks need to pay attention to performing server maintenance. Server maintenance is carried out periodically to maintain the operation of digital banking services and maintain service quality related to speed and accessibility. In the long term, it is necessary to take into account the replacement of server hardware at least once to be able to keep up with the development of information technology. Additionally, it is essential to register for new EB features that align with customer expectations. Implementing these new features will diversify the product portfolio and better meet customer needs. The ease with which this category is navigated can improve customer perception of speed and overall performance. As customers easily use these new features, their perception of service processing speed will increase.

Performing processing speed assessments for each application feature should be done regularly to identify bugs and create shortcuts to the process of each feature on the app. The possibility of changing the process should be considered to speed up each feature of the EB app. Banks also need to conduct periodic reviews of website features. Evaluation of website features can be done periodically using big data obtained from online chat features, allowing customers to provide live inputs to improve website features, including the process of displaying and navigating product catalogues on EB. The network system is one of the decisive factors for the quality of online banking services, so it is necessary to calculate and review the network used accurately. This, of course, also involves network costs that need to be carefully considered. Analysis and evaluation to maintain service quality not only with a single-layer backup but also with the concept of double-layer backup.

The results also show that CST have a positive effect on OPF. The results also confirm the mediating role of OPF and CST, which shows the importance of enhancing customer satisfaction and operational performance. Commercial banks need to invest heavily in improving user experience on digital platforms. This includes designing a user-friendly, easy-to-use, and mobile-optimized interface. Banks should also provide 24/7 technical support to promptly resolve customer issues. This not only improves CST but also helps maintain CLT. In particular, regularly updating and upgrading the system will ensure that customers always have the best experience.

Security is always one of the most important factors for customers when using EB services. Banks need to invest in advanced security technologies such as two-factor authentication, data encryption, and transaction monitoring systems to detect and prevent fraud. Training employees and customers on basic security measures is also an effective way to mitigate risks. Transparency in information about the privacy policy and how to handle problems will help customers feel more secure when using the service. In addition, banks should regularly check and re-evaluate their security systems to ensure they are always working effectively. The safety of transactions will create a solid trust for customers.

Commercial banks should focus on building personalised relationships with customers through EB services. This can be achieved by using technologies such as artificial intelligence to analyse customer behaviour and preferences, thereby providing tailored recommendations and services. Sending personalized notifications, reminders, and promotions also helps customers feel cared for. In addition, banks need to maintain regular communication with customers through online channels such as email, mobile applications, and social media. Listening to and responding quickly to customer feedback will help strengthen this relationship. Finally, the organisation's loyalty programme will create an incentive for customers to continue using the bank's services.

To increase CLT, commercial banks need to provide added value and unique services through digital platforms. This can include personal financial advisory services, automated financial management tools, and flexible savings and investment programs. The bank may also partner with other companies to provide additional services such as online shopping, bill payments, and other utility services. Implementing promotions and special offers for loyal customers will also serve as a great motivator. Additionally, developing mobile apps with advanced features and a user-friendly interface will improve the user experience. Finally, the creation of new financial services and products, meeting the changing needs of customers, will help the bank always maintain a competitive position in the market.

This research yields significant theoretical and practical contributions. Theoretically, the study expands the application of the Theory of Planned Behaviour (TPB) in the field of Electronic Banking (EB) services. In particular, the integration of TPB with aspects of EB, such as seamlessness, personalisation, and technology integration, adds a new layer of understanding to this theory in the context of digital transformation. In practical terms, the study provides a basis for banks to optimise EB services by improving the quality of experience factor, thereby promoting customer service behaviour. At the same time, the research results help financial managers better understand the role of customer awareness and behaviour in designing appropriate service strategies, contributing to improving competitiveness and promoting the sustainable development of Vietnam's banking industry in the digital era.

Research limitations

The study assessed the effect of SQE and OPF on CST and CLT in Vietnamese commercial banks. However, the study still has some limitations in sample size due to time and financial limitations. Therefore, further studies may increase the sample size to obtain more comprehensive results. In addition, besides the factors mentioned in the research model, there may also be other factors

affecting CLT at Vietnamese commercial banks. Therefore, further studies can be calibrated and supplemented to more comprehensively study on CLT of Vietnamese commercial banks.

Conflicts of interest declaration

No potential conflict of interest was reported by the authors.

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